

Triterpene constituents and antibacterial activity of the stems of *Reissantia grahamii*

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Abstract : The stems of the medicinal plant *Reissantia grahamii* has furnished a new triterpenoid designated reissantadiol (1) together with friedelin, pachysandiol-A, canophyllol, endodesmiadiol (2) and abruslactone-A (3). Structures 1, 2 and 3 were established from extensive 1D and 2D NMR studies. Preliminary antibacterial activity studies on crude ethyl acetate extract of defatted stems showed strong activity against bacterial strains *Escherichia coli* strain V (Verotoxigenic *E. coli*), *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Vibrio cholerae* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

Keywords : Pentacyclic triterpene, reissantadiol, endodesmiadiol, abruslactone-A, antibacterial activity, *Reissantia grahamii*.

Introduction

Powder or decoction of the leaves and bark of *Reissantia grahamii* (Wight) Ding Hou syn. *Pristimera grahamii* A.C. Smith (Family : Celastraceae) is used by the tribes of Maharashtra, India for chronic cough, aches and joint pain. It is also claimed to be useful in urinary disorders and skin diseases. The roots are reported to have antibiotic properties¹ and there seems to be no other report. This plant is used in Bihar, India for the treatment of paralysis. "The crushed leaves and stems are applied to wounds infested with maggots"². Earlier workers have reported the isolation of pristimerin, dulcitol from the root bark³, pristirol from root⁴ while leaves of this plant yielded erythrodiol, stigmastadien-3 β -ol⁵, pristimeronol⁶ and grahamidiol⁷. We worked on the chemical constituents of the stems as there was no report on its chemical

investigation till date, and our interest in this regard was further prompted by our observation of the bactericidal activity of the crude extract of the stems. Herein, we report the isolation and characterization of a new friedelane reissantadiol (1) and the known triterpenoids friedelin, 2 α ,28-dihydroxyfriedelan-3-one (2), canophyllol, pachysandiol and abruslactone-A (3) from the stems of the plant. This is so far the first occurrence of endodesmiadiol and abruslactone-A in a *Reissantia* species and second occurrence of endodesmiadiol in terrestrial plant. The results of preliminary bactericidal studies on the crude ethyl acetate extract of defatted stems and of a chromatographic fraction are also reported.

Results and discussion

Reissantadiol (1), isolated as a white amorphous pow-

der, showed ion peak (ES^+) at m/z 463.5164 for ($M.H_2O+H^+$) in QTOF MS in conformity with its molecular formula $C_{30}H_{52}O_2$. There was a strong IR absorption at 3439 cm^{-1} for the presence of hydroxyl group but had no absorption for $C=O$ group. The 1H spectrum displayed resonances for seven tertiary methyls and one secondary methyl in the region δ 0.77–1.19. Methine proton attached to carbon bearing one OH group appeared at δ 3.35 (1H, dd, J 11.1, 3.0 Hz) in conformity with its axial orientation and COSY experiment established that it was coupled with a methine proton signal at δ 4.04 (1H, dt, J 3.0, 3.0 Hz) in consonance with the presence of $2\alpha,3\alpha$ -diol unit in reissantiadiol (**1**). Similar 1H resonances are reported for congener pachysandiol-A (δ 3.54 and 3.99) for H-3 and H-2, respectively. Treatment of **1** with pyridine- Ac_2O furnished a diacetate derivative (**4**) further attributing the previous contention of **1** having two -OH groups. The ^{13}C NMR and DEPT-135 spectra adduced for the presence of 30 carbons involving 8 methyls, 10 methylenes, 6 methines and 6 quaternary carbons. In order to identify a proton signal and the signal for carbon to which it is attached a two-dimensional ^{13}C - 1H correlation (HSQC) experiment was run. Identification of the resonance for the non-protonated carbons and methylene carbons were not straightforward and for this purpose HMBC experiment was performed. Key correlations are summarised in structure A further supporting structure **1** for reissantiadiol. The carbon shifts assignments in **1** were verified by gradual downfield shift of the signals upon addition of $Eu(fod)_3-d_{27}$. The extent of the downfield shift decreased with increasing distance from coordinating Eu^{III} with hydroxyls. Incidentally this is the first report of the natural occurrence of reissantiadiol (**1**). It was previously derived from 3α -hydroxyfriedelan-2-one⁸.

The amorphous compound **2** readily formed a diacetate **5** upon treatment with Ac_2O -pyridine. Their spectral data is in agreement with cited literature for $2\alpha,28$ -dihydroxyfriedelane-3-one which was reported recently from *Endodesmia canophylloides* (Fam. Guttiferae) and designated endodesmiadiol⁹.

The presence of hydroxyl and lactonic carbonyl groups

for **3**, $C_{30}H_{46}O_3$ ($[M+1]^+$ m/z 455), was shown by the bands at 3550 and 1755 cm^{-1} in the IR spectrum. The 1H NMR spectrum of **3** presented signals for seven tertiary methyl groups, a signal attributed to a vinylic proton and two signals assigned to protons of carbinol type. The IR, 1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectral analysis, the latter revealing the presence of thirty signals including δ 182.6 (C-29), 140.2 (C-13), 124.7 (C-12), 78.9 (C-3) and 83.1 (C-22), were used to establish that compound **3** had the backbone of β -amyirin. Further, compound **3** exhibited 1H signal typical for axially oriented H-3. The MS spectrum of compound **3** presented a retro-Diels-Alder standard fragmentation [m/z 246 (base peak) and 207], indicating that the lactonic ring was localized at ring D and/or E. HSQC and HMBC spectral analyses further confirmed its structure as 3β -hydroxyolean-12-en-22,29-olide which was assigned to abruslactone-A isolated from *Abrus precatorius* (Fam. Leguminosae)¹⁰. The structure of abruslactone-A as **3** was determined by X-ray studies¹¹ and only scanty 1H NMR data available in current literature.

The ethyl acetate extract of *R. grahamii* showed inhibitory activity against a range of multidrug resistant bacteria including *V. cholerae* by agar-diffusion assay with significance ($p < 0.05$) (Fig. 1) as in Table 1. None of these extracts tested in the present study released hemoglobin from red blood cells and hence was not cytotoxic to human erythrocytes at the concentrations up to 40 mg/ml.

Table 1. Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) of *R. grahamii* extract and a eluate fraction against a range of pathogenic bacteria

	Antibacterial activity (mg/ml)			
	Sample 1		Sample 2	
	MIC	MBC	MIC	MBC
<i>B. subtilis</i> ATCC 6623	3.0	> 4.0	-	-
<i>E. coli</i> VT3	3.0	> 4.0	20.0	≥20.0
<i>V. cholerae</i> NB2	0.25	< 1.0	1.0	≤4.0
<i>P. aeruginosa</i> ATCC 15442	3.0	> 4.0	20.0	≥20.0
<i>S. aureus</i> ATCC 25923	1.0	> 1.0	0.25	0.5

MIC/MBC was not obtained within the range of concentration (up to 40 mg/ml) of the extract tested.

Fig. 1. Determination of effect of crude ethyl acetate extract (re-suspended in methanol) on (A) *B. subtilis*, (B) *E. coli*, (C) *P. aeruginosa*, (D) *S. aureus* and (E) *V. cholerae* strain NB2 by agar-diffusion assay method. Bacterial strains were spread on MHA. In each case, 100 μ L of 50 mg/ml of plant extract (in methanol).

Experimental

General :

IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer RXI FTIR spectrophotometer using KBr pellets, and ^1H (300 MHz) and ^{13}C (75 MHz) NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AV300 supercon NMR spectrometer working with Topspin 1.3 programme version in 5 mm BBO probe using CDCl_3 as solvent. Mass spectrum was taken on a Qtof Micro YA 263 spectrometer. Column chromatography was carried out on silica gel (SRL, India; 60–120 mesh). MPLC was carried out on EYELA 202 system with dual pump using silica gel (SRL, India; 230–400 mesh) column. TLC was performed on silica gel G plates.

Plant material :

The plant material was collected from Bhimashankar hill forests of Western Ghats (100 km off Pune) in the month of August 2006 and authenticated by Dr. S. Usman Ali, Former Head, Department of Pharmacognosy, Central Research Institute for Siddha, Chennai by comparison with the herbarium specimen (No. 53754/1967) available at B.S.I., Pune. A voucher specimen (No. SUA/14/2006) has been deposited in the herbarium of C.R.I. (Siddha), Chennai.

Extraction and isolation :

Air dried powdered stems (1.5 kg) of *R. grahamii* were extracted successively with petroleum ether and EtOAc at room temperature. The residue from petroleum ether fraction was subjected to repeated CC over silica gel that sequentially yielded friedelin, canophyllo¹² and pachysandiol-A¹² characterised by comparison with authentic samples (co-TLC, similarities in IR, ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra). EtOAc extract was resolved by MPLC using silica gel packing and eluting with EtOAc and then EtOAc-MeOH mixtures. The residue from EtOAc eluate fractions was subjected to preparative TLC using EtOAc-petroleum ether (3 : 2, v/v) whereby compound **1** (12 mg, R_f 0.6) was obtained. EtOAc-MeOH (3 : 1, v/v) eluates afforded a gummy mass that was further subjected to CC over silica gel. Preparative TLC of the crude mass obtained from the CH_2Cl_2 -MeOH (5 : 1, v/v) eluate on silica gel G furnished the compound **2** (15 mg) and **3** (5 mg) having R_f 0.6 and 0.72 in EtOAc-MeOH (17 : 3).

Preparation of acetate **4** and **5** :

Compound **1** (8 mg) dissolved in pyridine (0.5 ml) was treated with Ac_2O (0.5 ml) and kept at room temperature for 24 h. Solvents removed under reduced pressure and preparative TLC of the crude product using petroleum ether-EtOAc (85 : 15) as eluent afforded the acetylated derivative **4** (6 mg, R_f 0.37). Following the similar procedure acetate **5** was prepared from compound **2**.

^1H and ^{13}C NMR data and key HMBC correlations of compounds **1**, **3** and **4** (300 MHz and 75 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ in ppm, J in Hz) :

Compound **1** :

δ_{H} : 1.79 (1H, m, H_a -1), 1.84 (1H, m, H_b -1), 4.04 (1H, dt, J 3.0, 3.0 Hz, H-2), 3.35 (1H, dd, J 11.1, 3.0 Hz, H-3), 1.46 (1H, m, H-4), 1.74 (1H, m, H_a -6), 1.79 (1H, m, H_b -6), 1.34 (1H, m, H_a -7), 1.43 (1H, m, H_b -7), 1.33 (1H, br.s, H-8), 1.41 (1H, m, H-10), 1.16 (1H, m, H_a -11), 1.20 (1H, m, H_b -11), 1.30 (2H, m, H_2 -12), 1.27 (2H, m, H_2 -15), 1.53 (1H, m, H_a -16), 1.58 (1H, m, H_b -16), 1.54 (1H, m, H-18), 1.33 (1H, m, H_a -19), 1.37 (1H, m, 19- H_b), 1.48 (2H, m, H_2 -21), 0.92 (1H, m, H_a -22), 1.48 (1H, m, H_b -22), 0.88 (3H, d, J 6.1 Hz, H_3 -23), 0.77 (3H, s, H_3 -24), 0.81 (3H, s, H_3 -25), 1.01 (3H, s, H_3 -26), 0.99 (3H, s, H_3 -27), 1.19 (3H, s, H_3 -28), 0.99 (3H, s, H_3 -29), 0.94 (3H, s, H_3 -30).

δ_C : 26.7 (C-1), 69.8 (C-2), 73.4 (C-3), 45.7 (C-4), 37.9 (C-5), 41.1 (C-6), 17.8 (C-7), 53.0 (C-8), 36.5 (C-9), 51.4 (C-10), 35.3 (C-11), 30.6 (C-12), 39.7 (C-13), 38.3 (C-14), 32.4 (C-15), 36.0 (C-16), 28.2 (C-17), 42.8 (C-18), 35.4 (C-19), 28.2 (C-20), 32.8 (C-21), 39.3 (C-22), 9.8 (C-23), 13.5 (C-24), 17.9 (C-25), 18.7 (C-26), 20.2 (C-27), 32.1 (C-28), 31.7 (C-29), 35.1 (C-30).

HMBC (H→C) H-2→C-4, C-10; H-4→C-3, C-7; H-6→C-8; H-7→C-14; H-8→C-13; H-10→C-25; H-11→C-12; H-12→C-14; H-15→C-17; H-16→C-14; H-18→C-17, C-28; H-19→C-28, C-30; H-21→C-22; H-23→C-3, C-4, C-5; H-24→C-4, C-5, C-6, C-10; H-25→C-10, C-11; H-26→C-12, C-14, C-18; H-27→C-12, C-13, C-14; H-28→C-16, C-17, C-18; H-29→C-20, C-22, C-30; H-30→C-20, C-29.

Compound 3 :

δ_H : 1.48 (2H, m, H₂-1), 1.20 (1H, m, H_a-2), 1.88 (1H, m, H_b-2), 3.21 (1H, dd, *J* 10.2, 5.7 Hz, H-3), 1.56 (1H, m, H-5), 0.88 (1H, m, H_a-6), 1.54 (1H, m, H_b-6), 1.40 (2H, m, H₂-7), 1.54 (1H, m, H-9), 1.87 (1H, m, H_a-11), 1.88 (1H, m, H_b-11), 5.30 (1H, t, *J* 3.8 Hz),

1.18 (2H, m, H₂-15), 1.78 (2H, m, H₂-16), 2.12 (1H, m, H-18), 1.48 (1H, m, H_a-19), 1.92 (1H, m, H_b-19), 1.94 (1H, m, H_a-21), 2.24 (1H, m, H_b-21), 4.14 (1H, d, *J* 5.5 Hz, H-22), 0.99 (3H, s, H₃-23), 0.79 (3H, s, H₃-24), 0.94 (3H, s, H₃-25), 0.93 (3H, s, H₃-26), 0.87 (3H, s, H₃-27), 1.07 (3H, s, H₃-28), 1.21 (3H, s, H₃-30).

δ_C : 33.1 (C-1), 25.2 (C-2), 78.9 (C-3), 37.0 (C-4), 47.5 (C-5), 18.3 (C-6), 33.4 (C-7), 39.3 (C-8), 47.5 (C-9), 37.0 (C-10), 23.5 (C-11), 124.7 (C-12), 140.2 (C-13), 39.5 (C-14), 24.3 (C-15), 24.2 (C-16), 35.3 (C-17), 43.5 (C-18), 39.8 (C-19), 42.5 (C-20), 33.8 (C-21), 83.1 (C-22), 28.1 (C-23), 15.4 (C-24), 15.4 (C-25), 17.0 (C-26), 24.9 (C-27), 24.1 (C-28), 182.6 (C-29), 21.0 (C-30).

HMBC (H→C) H-1→C-10; H-2→C-3; H-5→C-3; H-7→C-6; H-9→C-14; H-12→C-9, C-11; H-21→C-19, C-29; H-22→C-20, C-28; H-23→C-4, C-24; H-24→C-4, C-23; H-25→C-8, C-10; H-26→C-8, C-9; H-27→C-15, C-18; H-28→C-16, C-18; H-30→C-21, C-29.

Compound 4 :

δ_H : 1.79 (1H, m, H_a-1), 1.84 (1H, m, H_b-1), 5.32

(1H, m, H-2), 4.71 (1H, dd, *J* 11.3, 3.2 Hz, H-3), 1.70 (1H, m, H-4), 1.50 (2H, m, H₂-6), 1.34 (1H, m, H-7), 1.43 (1H, m, H_b-7), 1.33 (1H, br.s, H-8), 1.41 (1H, m, H-10), 1.16 (1H, m, H_a-11), 1.20 (1H, m, H_b-11), 1.30 (2H, m, H₂-12), 1.27 (2H, m, H₂-15), 1.53 (1H, m, H_a-16), 1.58 (1H, m, H-16), 1.51 (1H, m, H-18), 1.33 (1H, m, H_a-19), 1.37 (1H, m, H_b-19), 1.48 (2H, m, H₂-21), 0.92 (1H, m, H-22), 1.48 (1H, m, H_b-22), 0.87 (3H, d, *J* 6.2 Hz, H₃-23), 0.77 (3H, s, H₃-24), 0.81 (3H, s, H₃-25), 1.01 (3H, s, H₃-26), 0.99 (3H, s, H₃-27), 1.19 (3H, s, H₃-28), 0.99 (3H, s, H₃-29), 0.94 (3H, s, H₃-30), 1.99 (3H, s, 3-OCOCH₃), 2.10 (3H, s, 2-OCOCH₃).

δ_C : 24.9 (C-1), 69.7 (C-2), 73.8 (C-3), 43.8 (C-4), 38.2 (C-5), 40.9 (C-6), 17.8 (C-7), 52.8 (C-8), 36.4 (C-9), 52.4 (C-10), 35.3 (C-11), 30.4 (C-12), 39.7 (C-13), 38.3 (C-14), 32.3 (C-15), 36.1 (C-16), 30.0 (C-17), 42.7 (C-18), 35.2 (C-19), 28.1 (C-20), 32.8 (C-21), 39.1 (C-22), 9.3 (C-23), 13.6 (C-24), 18.0 (C-25), 18.6 (C-26), 20.1 (C-27), 32.1 (C-28), 31.8 (C-29), 34.9 (C-30), 170.0 (2-OCOCH₃), 20.8 (2-OCOCH₃), 170.5 (3-OCOCH₃), 21.3 (3-OCOCH₃).

Antibacterial activity :

Bacterial strains :

The bacterial strains used in this study were *Vibrio cholerae* O1 (NB2), *Escherichia coli* strain VT3 (Verotoxigenic *E. coli*), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 15442, *E. coli* ATCC 25922, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923 and *Bacillus subtilis* ATCC 6623. Strains were stored in 15% glycerol stock at -70 °C. Crude EtOAc extract of the plant (sample 1) and EtOAc-MeOH (3 : 1) eluate fraction (sample 2) from chromatography of the aforesaid extract were used in this study.

Screening for antibacterial activity :

Antibacterial activity of the extract was determined by agar-diffusion assay¹³. Bacterial strains were first grown in Mueller-Hinton broth (MHB) (HiMedia) under shaking condition for 4 h at 37 °C and after the incubation period culture were spread on Mueller-Hinton agar (MHA) (HiMedia) at 0.5 McFarland. The wells were made using sterile 6 mm cork borer in the inoculated MHA plate. The wells were filled with 100 μ L of the plants extracts (re-suspended in MeOH) and blanks (MeOH). The concentrations of extract employed were 100 mg/ml. Tetracycline (150 μ g/ml, 200 μ L) was used as antibacterial

positive control and *E. coli* ATCC 25922 was included for quality assurance. Zone diameter was measured after 24 h incubation at 37 °C. The photograph was taken in Gel documentation system (Vilber Lourmat, France).

Determination of minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) :

MIC and MBC of *Reissantia grahamii* extract were assessed as described previously¹⁴ using the broth microdilution method recommended by the National Committee for Clinical Laboratory Standards^{15,16}. An inoculum of the microorganism was prepared from 24 h MHB cultures and suspensions were adjusted with a turbidity equivalent to that of a 0.5 McFarland standard. Suspensions were further diluted 1 : 10 in sterile MHB to obtain a final inoculum of 5×10^5 CFU/ml. The 96-well round bottom sterile plates were prepared by dispensing 180 μ L of the inoculated broth into each well. A 20 μ L aliquot of the plant extract was added. The concentrations of plant extract tested were 0.025, 0.05, 0.1, 0.25, 0.5, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 10, 20 and 40 mg/ml. Dilutions of ampicillin served as positive control, while broth with 20 μ L of MeOH was used as negative control. The ATCC strain *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 was included for quality assurance purposes. Plates were covered and incubated for 24 h in ambient air at 37 °C. After incubation, minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC) were read visually; all wells were plated to nutrient agar (Hi-Media) and incubated. The minimal bactericidal concentration (MBC) was defined as a 99.9% reduction in CFU from the starting inoculum after 24 h incubation interval.

Determination of cellular toxicity using human erythrocytes :

Hemolysis test was employed to determine cellular toxicity of the extract as previously described¹⁷. Plant extracts at concentrations ranging from 6 to 40 mg/ml, were incubated with an equal volume of 1% human red blood cells in phosphate buffered saline (10 mM PBS, pH 7.4) at 37 °C for 1 h. Non-hemolytic and 100% hemolytic controls were the buffer alone and the buffer containing 1% Triton X-100, respectively. Cell lysis was monitored by measuring the release of hemoglobin at 540 nm.

Conclusion :

A new friedelane reissantadiol (1) along with four known analogous triterpenes and one oleanane abruslactone-A were isolated from the stems of *Reissantia*

grahamii. It is interesting to note that the crude extracts of the stems of *R. grahamii* were significantly effective against the strains of *V. cholerae* and *S. aureus*, the causative agents of the dreadful disease, cholera and gastrointestinal disorders such as food poisoning, respectively. Furthermore, *V. cholerae* NB2 was resistant to co-trimoxazole, furazolidone, nalidixic acid, streptomycin, and tetracycline, which are generally used to treat the cholera patients. In addition, to the best of our knowledge, the plant extracts used in this study are being shown for the first time to demonstrate bactericidal activity against *V. cholerae* and *S. aureus*, the causative agents of different enteropathogenic outbreaks. The extracts are also effective against the strains *E. coli* strain V (Verotoxigenic *E. coli*), *B. subtilis* and *P. aeruginosa*. In this connection a recent report has however dealt with antimicrobial and phytotoxic study of pure friedelin¹⁸ and antiplasmodial activity of endodesmiadiol⁹.

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